

DEVELOPING A FRAMEWORK AS A TACTICAL APPROACH TO BOOST CREATIVITY IN WRITING INSTRUCTION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14877162>

Said Azman VAHID NUR,

Professor of Faculty of Languages & Communication, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia

Abstract. The Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) emphasizes the advancement of human capital in educational environments. This creates a need for educators who can introduce innovative mindsets to English Language instruction, as highlighted in the National Education Blueprint (NEP) and the Integrated Curriculum for Secondary Schools (KSSM), aligning with the 21st Century Teaching and Learning framework. Despite an array of pedagogical resources and methodologies available for teaching writing creatively, some educators still lack the creative competencies and expertise to adopt, incorporate, and implement instructional strategies that enhance students' engagement and writing proficiency.

Keywords: qualitative study, strategic solution, writing skills, 21st century teaching, creative teaching strategies, ESL, learning, module development.

A preliminary qualitative study was conducted with four ESL educators in secondary schools in Selangor to support the analysis phase of the actual module development initiative. The primary aim of this study was to explore the obstacles teachers encounter in teaching writing innovatively. Data gathered through semi-structured interviews and observations led to a strategic resolution for cultivating creative pedagogies suited to the present academic landscape.

This study concludes that a module should be conceptualized and constructed, encompassing a repertoire of creative teaching strategies applicable across multiple proficiency levels. It also suggests that students will be empowered to take ownership of their writing skills as a result. Furthermore, a standardized set of benchmarks should be established by educational authorities to assess creative instruction, serving as a guideline for teachers.

In fulfilling the demand of preparing top-notch human capital in the 4th Industrial Revolution, it is imperative that a language teacher integrates the six global competencies of 21st century education in the classroom which includes creativity other than character, citizenship, collaboration, communication, and critical thinking.¹

Based Curriculum as well as Secondary School Integrated Curriculum in line with the 21st-century teaching and learning philosophy. Similarly, the Common European Framework for Reference (CEFR), which consists of the creativity assessment scales for writing, is an international teaching and learning framework and assessment tool adopted currently in Malaysia, to measure the competency and proficiency of creativity in writing. Given its emphasis in the national curriculum, there is an urgent need for teachers, facilitators, and educators to harness and increase creativity among Malaysian learners, starting from a young age through creative teaching and learning in ESL classes to prepare the country for 4IR (Mohd, Nur, Tuan, & Hazrati, 2018). Yet, when common practice in ESL classrooms across the country is reviewed, there seems to be troubling discrepancy. Students' achievement in terms of scores and results are given more emphasis, which is rigidly governed by the curriculum (Annuar, 1998).

Teaching is not seen as a cultivation of creativity, but merely as a transfer of knowledge, owing to the Malaysian or Asian culture whereby everything they teacher says is mandatory. Going against such an authority becomes an offence and is considered morally unethical (Lau,

¹ Fullan, M., Quinn, J., & McEachen, J. (2018). *New pedagogies fro deep learning. Leading transformation in schools, districts and systems.* Thousands Oaks, US: SAGE Publications Inc.

Hui, & Ng, 2004). By right, having the access and exposure to the latest learning gadgets and platforms, students should always be improving and be motivated to learn writing. Unfortunately, the bitter reality is that students do not have the interest and/or are unwilling to learn writing in spite of having technology at their fingertips. This could be due to the insufficient creativity on how to make effective use of learning materials that can benefit them. Although many programs have been initiated by the Ministry of Education to polish the English Language achievement in Malaysia, writing skills are still one of the on-going, difficult, and notable concerns in Malaysian ESL classrooms² Writing skills do not depend solely on attitude and talent, but also on the teachers' creativity in teaching strategies and use of materials in the ESL classroom³ Lack of knowledge and skills to adopt, integrate, and apply new pedagogical approaches would hinder students from writing efficiently because the writing techniques necessitate specific strategies to produce a comprehensive and quality content to achieve the requirement of the writing assessment rubrics⁴

According to Maley and Peachy a vast pool of sources in various forms is available for teachers to teach creatively. This instills creative thinking skills and intelligence while further facilitating creativity in language teaching and learning. These creative activities are powerful enough to foster creative behavior among learners especially when the tasks are student-centric and employ communicative approaches. Creativity in language teaching mainly concerns the individual, prior to the teaching and learning process and the end-result⁵. Hence, creativity is derived from a creative individual first, in this case, the teacher, who then influences the thinking and decision-making processes, subsequently contributing to the end product generated. Creativity does not blossom spontaneously in an individual or an ESL classroom, but this does not mean that it is not an innate ability. Creativity can be enhanced and taught, although it is complex and requires cognitive abilities to complete a task.⁶

According to Bohm everyone is born creative, and if nourished well, creativity could flourish. The root starts from home before progressing in schools, where learning becomes flexible, unique, and creative. Setting a benchmark for creativity is challenging. Within the Malaysian setting, creativity is highly in demand for an individual to grow in all aspects holistically and able to serve the nation to support the educational revolution (Halim, 2009). This preliminary study was carried out to identify teachers' hardships in the teaching of writing creativity and to propose a strategic solution to fill the gap in creative teaching strategies, as well as to fulfill the newest demand in the teaching of writing. Therefore, to address the needs analysis phase of a module development and a strategic solution, a writing module would be introduced; it will consist of a variety of strategies for teaching creative writing skills. The module will focus on strategies that teach writing creatively to improve students' grade in Section B: Continuous Writing, which allocates the highest marks i.e. 50 out of 85 marks, for the SPM or Sijil Pelajaran Malaysia (National Examination) English Paper 1, 1119/1. Thus, this paper precedes the needs analysis phase of developing the Creative Teaching of Writing Module, by addressing the preliminary research questions (i), the challenges faced by teachers to teach writing creatively, and (ii) the teachers' need for a module.

Kutner, Olson, Warner, and Hertzog⁷ state that there is no definitive way to determine the minimum sample for qualitative research as it is influenced and driven by many factors. In most

² Ilyana, J., Paramasivam, S., Husain, S., & Bakar, R. A. (2015). The consistency between writing self-efficacy and writing performance. *Journal of Language* <https://doi.org/10.17507/jltr.0603.09>. *Teaching and Research*, 6(3)

³ Supyan, Maarof, & D'cruz, 2001

⁴ Seman, Yusoff, & Embong, 2017

⁵ Fisher, 2004

⁶ Fawcett, 2002

⁷ Arkün, S., & Akkoyunlu, B. (2008). A study on the development process of a multimedia learning environment according to the ADDIE model and students' opinions of the multimedia learning environment. *Interactive Educational Multimedia*, 17, 1-19.

qualitative studies, purposeful sampling is employed because it allows researchers to gather rich information and gain insights related to the research questions. As such, the primary source of data for the present study is a semi structured interview conducted with 4 ESL participants who were Form Four teachers from two semi-urban schools in Selangor. With 15 to 22 years of service, these teachers had taught lower and upper secondary school students at both urban and rural schools and they held positions that included overseeing the English Language Panel, coordinating PT3 and SPM examinations, grading SPM papers, becoming CEFR master trainers and SISC coaches, judging co-academic events, as well as handling Language competitions at the state level. Considering the module for the future project is tailored for the upper secondary school students, the selection of the teacher informants was appropriate. Thematic analysis was conducted based on Miles and Huberman (1994). The interview protocol was divided into 2 sub-sections: (a) Challenges Faced in Teaching Writing Creatively and (b) the assistance needed in teaching writing creatively. In brief, when conducting teaching and learning, teachers who possess sufficient knowledge and skills in teaching ESL writing skills creatively, will employ and utilize all the possible materials and resources, methods and techniques, and approaches in teaching strategies, as well as tailor-made styles to suit the various levels of students. Teachers' knowledge is identified as by the acquisition of skills that assist teaching and learning practices. Teachers are deemed knowledgeable if they are well-versed in information, concepts, theories, models, and frameworks that will be the foregrounds of the teaching and learning objectives. Meanwhile, skills are the abilities of putting the knowledge in practical mode, such as creatively creating a learning condition, and dedicatedly improving the language skills of diverse students. Moreover, teachers should promote various and integrated teaching procedures that are appropriate to the content and objectives, as well as continuously supervise students' performance.

The teachers are characterized qualified as they are particular about their lessons and students' homework, stern in rectifying mistakes and corrections, and focused on scores and accurate performance. Nevertheless, nowadays, a creative teacher is a role model who leaves an imprint though creative lessons, thus, inspiring students to be interested and motivated to learn English or even become someone like them in the future. Unfortunately, when probed on the reasons for teachers' becoming less enthusiastic with this investment, three main themes were identified. The identified themes that contribute to this phenomenon are (i) teachers' skills and knowledge in being creative, (ii) student's language proficiency and (iii) inadequate guidance and facilities for teaching creatively. They agreed that being creative all the time in an ESL class, especially during writing lessons, leaves great impacts on students' interest and end-results, but causes two major setbacks. The two sub-themes that emerged were the lack of impact from creative teaching of writing and the lack of creativity in teaching strategies. The blending of strategies has to be powerful to leave an imprint in students' learning satisfaction, so that they can finally learn something new or correctly and are able to use it appropriately in their writing. Teaching for creativity should be followed by the assessment for students' creative output. Teachers who teach creatively usually possess a wealth of foundation in the English Language and are able to derive lessons based on their knowledge and imagination, which provide sense or meaning at the end of the lesson (Jones, 2012). These teachers can quickly produce engaging activities from minimal materials or without any material at all.

Lack of Creativity in Teaching Strategies According to the participants, some teachers are less likely to step out of their common teaching strategies or be willing to learn new things by adopting, integrating, and applying creative teaching strategies to enhance and boost students' interest and achievement in writing. They mentioned that there is a lack of self-initiative pursuit among the younger teachers, probably because they are still in the initial stages of catching up with the reality in the practical methods of teaching, since most items are taught differently from how they are practiced in an actual setting. Their main concern and responsibility are to maintain

discipline and ensure that students are well guided, especially in a standard, large classroom of 40 students with various capabilities⁸.

This is because creative learning materials and resources create an interesting environment that can boost students' interest in learning; thus, it is vital for teachers to emphasize the integration of various materials to enhance learning. 21st century teachers are suggested to be more updated with the latest occurrences and available technologies to be applied in creative teaching. For example, augmented reality can teach vocabulary; virtual reality can teach descriptive words and share information on places that students cannot access; Skype messaging can allow the exchange of ideas and information on content point development; whereas the use of various printed materials and actual physical movements can provide clearer examples to enhance understanding. Hence, this study proposes that these teachers may learn to be creative slowly and steadily through assisted printed materials e.g. modules, and may gain more exposure through workshops. Meanwhile, teachers who have been in the service for a long time seem to display apprehension toward technological growth, due to being unfamiliar with available gadgets that continue to be updated rapidly.

Hence, these teachers find it convenient to teach using their own personal styles and believe that certain traditional methods are culture oriented, inherited from the Asian teaching ethos. However, when the ministry highlights creativity in all policies and encourages it in the teaching pedagogy of all school levels, teachers may need to adjust accordingly by transforming their teaching strategies to be in line with the 21st century teaching and learning philosophy.

STRATEGIC SOLUTION: MODULE DEVELOPMENT

Creativity needs to be inserted into teaching and learning sessions to produce a productive and creative result (2018). Conventional teaching would limit the discovery of a teacher's creative potentials and a student's creativity in participation and interaction during writing class; this affects the process approach learning of writing, a notion also supported by Thulasi, Ismail, and Salam (2015). This notion is also in line with Seman et al. (2017) where skills and knowledge to incorporate materials, methods, strategies, techniques, resources, and approaches, by teachers using collaborative and communicative approaches, are essential in producing a quality writing that meets the requirement of the exam descriptors. Perhaps a writing module could be the solution for teachers to rely on for creative activities. Despite suggestions of creative lessons, teachers will have the flexibility to adapt, modify, and implement suitable ideas based on students' levels, age, teaching and learning objectives, and writing skills covered for the day. In fact, this will allow teachers to come up with ideas efficiently and effectively, with a material on one hand, and a mobile phone in on the other (Nordin, Hamzah, Yunus, & Embi, 2010). Hence, teachers are at the center stage to expand students' writing skills through creative pedagogical skills and knowledge (Jeffrey and Craft 2004) in teaching of writing. The knowledge produced through this module can increase teachers' knowledge and skills in creative teaching, through using integrated materials, methods, strategies, and resources. It simultaneously enhances students' writing skills through creativity, which may then boost their overall motivation towards writing. According to Richey, Klein, and Nelson (2004) the strength of the design and research for module development can be used to solve problems in a specific context. Module development, based on design and research, enables the development of a module that is efficient in solving the current problems faced by upper secondary school teachers and students. When knowledge and skills are improved, teaching becomes more meaningful.

In conclusion, creativity depends on the individual's initiative to blend skills and knowledge to generate creative pedagogies in the teaching of writing. With regard to the proposed evaluation for creative teaching, teachers' creativity in the teaching of writing should be given urgent emphasis to meet the constantly changing teaching situations. A modified SKMP 2.0 teacher's teaching and learning evaluation criteria on creativity is vital, while suggestions in

⁸ Maskit, 2013; Rosas & West, 2009

the form of writing modules can aid teachers' teaching and lesson planning for daily teaching practices that emphasize creative activities. This implies that the teaching of creative writing would carve a path for excellence, not only to generate creative teaching strategies to tackle essay writing, but also to improve students' interest and motivation by considering writing as a doable task. Thus, the activities and strategies proposed in the module would ease the burden of teachers in teaching writing. The module can be used as a compact and comprehensive tool for the teaching of writing, as its systematic and organized instructions may help teachers to convey knowledge and skills effectively and efficiently. The activities can be altered for teaching other skills like reading, speaking, and listening as well. Moreover, the development of this module would not only update teachers' knowledge and skills in teaching, but also assist them in completing the syllabus peacefully without neglecting the KSSM objectives that emphasize future creative skills. The content and titles planned in the module are hoped to help teachers plan and execute a detailed and quick process of teaching writing. This module would inspire and encourage other teachers from different fields to teach creatively using various sources.

Development involves building solutions with strategies, objectives, and goals of the identified areas to fulfil the missing knowledge and skills, along with resources (Jean, 2006). Meanwhile, the 'ADDIE' instructional design used in this study defines development as a process of producing instructional materials, tools, and supports based on design. The module is created based on the needs phase of an evaluation phase (Arkün & Akkoyunlu, 2008). This study adopts the characteristics of the ADDIE model, where the development of the module is a detailed plan prepared with components from the teaching and learning environment. Funding: This research was funded by the grant from the Faculty of Education, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, Bangi, Selangor (GG-2018-001 and GG-2019-009). Competing Interests: The authors declare that they have no competing interests. Acknowledgement: All authors contributed equally to the conception and design of the study.

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